

Poly(vinyl propionate) and Poly(ethyl acrylate)— A Miscible Polymer Pair†

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A new miscible polymer pair, *viz.* poly(vinyl propionate) (PVPr) and poly(ethyl acrylate) (PEA) is reported. Blends of these polymers form clear films, clear solutions in common solvents and have single glass transition temperatures. Miscibility of these two polymers in binary combinations with poly(methyl acrylate) (PMA) or poly(vinyl acetate) (PVA) was also examined. Differential scanning calorimetry (D.S.C.) reveals that PVPr+PVA, PEA+PVA, PMA+PVPr and PMA+PEA are immiscible, although the first three pairs form clear films.

MISCIBLE blends of polymers are of rare occurrence^{1,2}. This situation arises because mixing of molecules of similar chemical nature is usually associated with small positive heat of mixing. In the case of small molecules this positive heat of mixing does not pose a problem towards homogeneous mixing because its unfavourable effect is outweighed by the combinatorial entropy of mixing which is positive. For polymer-polymer mixtures, the value of the latter per unit volume is exceedingly small in comparison to that for mixtures of small molecules due to the much smaller number of molecules involved in the former systems. The heat of mixing per unit volume, on the other hand, is a function of the number of segmental contacts which remains nearly constant with increase in molecular size. The result is that for polymer-polymer mixtures, the heat of mixing becomes the determining factor for miscibility.

An additional unfavourable factor arises from the difference in the free volumes of the components which results in a positive non-combinatorial free energy of mixing³. Thus, unless the components of a binary polymer mixture are so similar in chemical properties that the heat of mixing is zero or very near to it and also unless they are similar in physical properties, is homogeneous mixing of like polymers achieved. However, unlike the polymer pairs which have complimentary similarity, those having complimentary dissimilarity are miscible because the mixing is exothermic in such cases due to the presence of strong specific interactions between them⁴. The latter may be regarded as a manifestation of the existence of complimentary dissimilarity between polymer pairs.

Nevertheless, there exist few examples of pairs of like polymers which are miscible. Recently, we have reported that the like polymer pair PVA, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{OCOCH}_3)-$, and PMA, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{COOCH}_3)-$, is miscible and their miscibility is not due to the existence of any complimentary dissimilarity between them⁵. This system must therefore

be associated with an exceedingly small heat of mixing. This is not unlikely as the repeating unit of the two polymer molecules differ only in the orientation of the COO group as would be evident from their chemical structures shown above. They also do not differ much in physical properties⁶. Their T_g values differ by about 30° (T_g of PVA is 32° and that of PMA is 3°)⁷. It occurred to us that the higher homologues of these two polymers having the same number of carbon atoms in their respective repeating units might be miscible. We hypothesised that the next higher homologues, *viz.* PVPr, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{OCOCH}_2\text{CH}_3)-$ and PEA, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3)-$, stand in better stead than the PVA+PMA system with regard to the similarity in chemical properties inasmuch as their hydrogenated monomers are identical, being ethyl propionate for both. If the hydrogenated monomers are approximated as polymer segments⁸, the heat of mixing, due to exchange interaction, should be approximately zero and smaller than that for PVA+PMA systems for which the hydrogenated monomers, although very similar, are not identical. Also, the difference in the T_g values of PVPr and PEA is about 34° which is similar to that for PVA and PMA system (T_g of PVPr is 10° and that of PEA is -24°)⁶. Hence, the difference in free volumes of the components in this blend will also be of the same order as between PMA and PVA. We report here a preliminary study of the miscibility of PVPr and PEA.

It would be also of interest to examine whether the other binary blends obtainable from the four polymers PMA, PEA, PVA and PVPr are miscible. This paper reports also the results of preliminary investigations on the miscibility of these blends.

Experimental

The solvents were of reagent grade. They were dried and distilled before use. Ethyl acrylate monomer was an I.P.C.L. product.

† Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

Fig. 1. The ^1H nmr spectra of vinyl propionate in CCl_4 with TMS as internal standard

Vinyl propionate was synthesised from vinyl acetate and propionic acid by the vinyl interchange reaction following Adelman⁵. Anhydrous propionic acid was obtained from L.R. grade propionic acid (Loba) by fractional distillation using a column (1 m long) packed with porcelain rings (3 mm). Vinyl acetate (L.R.) was dried over CaCl_2 and distilled under reduced pressure. Vinyl acetate (25 mol), mercuric acetate (11.5 g), concentrated H_2SO_4 (3 g) and copper acetate (0.5 g) were mixed in a 5 liter 3-necked flask provided with a mercury-seal stirrer. The flask was cooled to 20° . Anhydrous propionic acid (4 mol) was added slowly while stirring. Stirring was continued for 2 h after which it was stopped and the reaction mixture in the stoppered flask was allowed to stand at 30° for 72 h. The reaction was stopped by the addition of sodium acetate (12 g) and the mixture was fractionally distilled at reduced pressure using the same column as described above. The fraction boiling in the range $48\text{--}52^\circ$ at 16.5–17.2 cm Hg pressure, was collected and refractionated under reduced pressure using propionic acid as a chaser and copper acetate (0.2 g) as polymerisation inhibitor. Pure vinyl propionate was obtained in 30% yield. The ^1H nmr spectra of the material (Fig 1) recorded using a Varian T-60 instrument at room temperature showed it to be pure. The resonances due to the various protons are indicated in the figure.

PEA ($\bar{M}_n = 773\,000$) was prepared by the solution polymerisation of the monomer in benzene (20%, v/v) at 60° under a nitrogen atmosphere using 2,2'-azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) as initiator (0.1%, w/v). The polymerisation was carried to 20% conversion and the polymer was isolated by precipitating into

petroleum ether (b.p. $40\text{--}60^\circ$). The polymer was purified by dissolution in benzene and precipitation into petroleum ether.

PVPr ($\bar{M}_n = 34\,700$) was prepared by polymerising vinyl propionate in bulk using AIBN initiator (0.1%, w/v) at 60° in an ampoule which was provided with a vacuum stopcock and a teflon coated stirring bar. The monomer was thoroughly degassed in a high vacuum line to 2×10^{-5} torr using the standard freeze-thaw technique. Polymerisation was continued for a pre-determined time (1.5 h) to keep the conversion low (ca. 15%) in order to minimise branching. After polymerisation the monomer was distilled off the polymerised solution in the high vacuum line into a similar ampoule in which a calculated amount of initiator was previously introduced. The monomer was again degassed and the polymerisation conducted at 60° as before. This procedure was repeated 6 times. Increasingly lesser time was required to achieve similar conversion as the recovery and polymerisation cycle progressed. In this way 30 g polymer was obtained from 55 g monomer and 15 g monomer still remained. The polymer was isolated by dissolving it in benzene and precipitating into petroleum ether. All the 6 batches of polymers were mixed and purified by dissolving in benzene and precipitating into petroleum ether. All polymer samples were finally dried in a vacuum-oven at 100° for 3 days. The preparation of the blends was already described⁵. PMA was a fractionated sample ($\bar{M}_v = 705\,940$) described earlier⁵. PVA was a whole polymer (AYAF-419) ($\bar{M}_v = 98\,000$) obtained from Union Carbide Corporation (U.S.A.).

Casting film of polymer blends : A 2% solution of the two polymers in the desired ratio was poured in a Petri dish which was then kept in a desiccator over CaCl_2 . The desiccator was provided with a small opening for the evaporation of the solvent. The clarity of the film was examined visually. The blend was isolated by wetting the film with water and dried in a vacuum-oven at 100° for 3 days and used for T_g measurements.

Determination of miscibility of blends in common solvent : Required amounts of polymer blends of known compositions and solvents were weighed into 6 mm glass tubes (Corning). The tubes were sealed and the clarity of the solutions was examined after an equilibration period of 96 h.

Determination of glass transition temperature (T_g) : The T_g 's were measured using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-2C or a DSC-2 differential scanning calorimeter (D.S.C.) calibrated with indium, water and n-octane. The blends were held at 373 K in the D.S.C. apparatus for 15 min and then quenched to 200 K where they were held for 5 min. The samples were then scanned at the heating rate of 20 K min^{-1} for the PEA+PVPr blends and 10 K min^{-1} for others from 200 to 373 K. T_g values were taken as the onset of the change of slope in the heat capacity plot determined by extrapolating both slopes to the point of intersection.

Molecular weight determinations : Intrinsic viscosity was determined in benzene at 30° . The following equations was used to obtain \bar{M}_n ; for poly(ethyl acrylate),

$$[\eta] = 27.7 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_n^{0.67}$$

and for poly(vinyl propionate) Buselli *et al.*¹⁰ used the equation for poly(vinyl acetate) given by Nakajima¹¹,

$$[\eta] = 8.91 \times 10^{-5} \bar{P}_n^{0.62}$$

Results and Discussion

In order to determine the miscibility of the two polymers PVPr and PEA, the clarity of the films of their blends was first examined. For this purpose the films were cast from four different solvents, *viz.* toluene, 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE), ethyl acetate (EtOAc) and acetone which represent four different chemical classes, *viz.* aromatic hydrocarbon, chlorinated aliphatic hydrocarbon, aliphatic ester and aliphatic ketone, respectively. Three blend compositions, *e.g.* PVPr : PEA = 3 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 by weight were tested; films of each blend composition being cast from all the four solvents. All the films turned out to be clear providing the first evidence that the polymer pair is miscible.

It should however be noted that the film clarity test alone does not provide unequivocal proof that a polymer pair is miscible. An immiscible pair may yield clear films if the refractive indices of the polymers are closely matched. On the other hand, a miscible polymer blend may yield an opaque

film if it is cast from a solvent, the strengths of interaction of which with the two polymers differ greatly¹².

A further test for the miscibility of the two polymers is to check the clarity of the solutions of the blends in common solvents. Clear solutions at all compositions are indicative of miscible polymer-polymer systems. However, a cloudy solution does not necessarily prove that the polymers are immiscible. For example, Patterson *et al.* showed theoretically as well as experimentally that a miscible polymer pair may yield a cloudy solution in a common solvent if the strengths of interaction of the solvents with the two polymers differ from each other, the maximum tolerable difference in the values of the χ parameters for obtaining clear solution depends on the molecular weights of the two polymers and the value of the thermodynamic interaction parameter between the miscible polymer pairs¹³⁻¹⁴. The polymer pair PEA+PVPr gives clear solutions at room temperature at all compositions in the two solvents tested, *viz.* acetone and toluene. This observation indicates that the two polymers are miscible at least at room temperature (*ca.* 32°).

Finally, the ultimate evidence in support of the homogeneity of the polymer blends is available from T_g studies. The differential scanning calorimetry (D.S.C.) traces of the polymer blends of PVPr+PEA at 7 different compositions along with those of the pure polymers are shown in Fig. 2. It is evident from the figure that each blend is characterised by a single T_g . The T_g 's of the blends lie in between the T_g values of the pure components.

Fig 2 The differential scanning calorimetry traces of the pure polymers PVPr and PEA and their blends. The weight fractions of PVPr in the blends for curves 1 through 9 are 1, 0.88, 0.75, 0.66, 0.50, 0.38, 0.25, 0.16 and 0, respectively.

From the above observations we conclude that PVPr and PEA are miscible in all proportions.

Thus, our expectation regarding their miscibility turns out to be correct. Further investigations with regard to construction of phase diagrams, determination of thermodynamic interaction parameter (χ_{23}) etc. between the components of this polymer pair are in progress in our laboratory.

Regarding the miscibility of the other blends obtainable from the four polymers PMA, PEA, PVA and PVPr, we note that six binary combinations are possible from these four polymers. These are PMA+PVA, PEA+PVPr, PMA+PEA, PVA+PVPr, PMA+PVPr and PEA+PVA. Of these we have shown here and earlier that the first two yield miscible blends⁶. The literature reports that solutions of PMA and PEA phase separate in many solvents and hence they are immiscible¹⁴. In agreement with this observation we have found that the blends of these two polymers form opaque films. All the remaining three pairs (at 1:1 w/w composition) form clear films when cast from benzene, toluene or acetone. However, the D.S.C. traces reproduced in Fig. 3 show that each of the two pairs, viz. PVA+PVPr and PEA+PVA exhibits two T_g 's indicating that these combinations

the 1:1 blend is included in Fig. 3. A shoulder is of course, noticed half way the D.S.C. trace for the 1:1 blend. From this observation and also from the immiscibility of the other pairs for which the carbon numbers of the repeating units are not equal, it is reasonable to conclude that PMA and PVPr are not miscible.

It may be concluded from this study that there exist good chances to find miscible binary blends from the combination of a polyvinyl ester and a polyacrylate when the carbon numbers of the repeating units are equal. This conclusion follows from the observation that PMA+PVA, and PEA+PVPr are miscible and from the arguments set forth in the introduction section.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express their sincere thanks to Mr. S. K. Ray, Department of Chemistry, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, for kindly performing the differential scanning calorimetry of the PEA+PVPr polymer blends using a Perkin-Elmer DSC-2C instrument. Thanks are also due to I.P.C.L., Baroda, and to Union Carbide Corporation, U.S.A., for gift samples of ethyl acrylate and PVA, respectively.

Fig. 8. D.S.C. traces of the polymer blends indicated in the figure.

make immiscible blends even though they give clear films. In the literature PEA and PVA have been stated to be compatible without, of course, any proof¹⁶. The T_g results just described do not support this view. The miscibility of the remaining pair PMA+PVPr could not be clearly established by D.S.C. because the T_g 's of the component polymers are too close to permit satisfactory resolution even though they exist two T_g 's. A D.S.C. trace for

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